

**ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' ACTIVITIES IN THE
SECURITIES MARKET**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the activities of commercial banks in the securities market of Uzbekistan, as well as the economic significance of operations carried out by banks in this market. Based on the results of the study, commercial banks, by actively participating in the capital market, have the potential to ensure financial stability of the economy, attract investment resources, and contribute to the development of the capital market. In addition, the article addresses issues related to the high share of state ownership and the need to increase the role of the private sector.

Keywords: Commercial bank, investment activity, securities, shares, bonds, underwriting, capital market.

Bringing the economy to a new stage of development and the growing demand for investment resources are encouraging commercial banks in Uzbekistan to expand their activities in the capital market and to seek new opportunities. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026" sets out the goals of increasing the level of digitalization of production and operational processes in the real sector of the economy and the financial and banking system to 70 percent by the end of 2026, as well as expanding capital market turnover from USD 200 million to USD 7 billion over the next five years¹. When these strategic objectives are achieved, the active participation of banks in the securities market as the main drivers of economic financing will become particularly important.

At the same time, a key challenge in the current banking system is the high share of state ownership in commercial banks. This situation may limit healthy competition, reduce banks' ability to adapt their legitimate activities to the demands of the modern economy, and lead to a decline in the quality of financial services. In order to address this issue, the Development Strategy for 2022–2026 provides for increasing the share of the private sector in the assets of state-owned commercial banks to 60 percent. This, in turn, will enhance the competitiveness of banks, strengthen their financial stability, and expand their opportunities for active participation in the securities market.

Thus, by actively participating in the securities market, commercial banks not only enhance their own investment capacity but also make a significant contribution to the development of the country's capital market, the attraction of investment resources, and the maintenance of economic stability.

Literature Review

Commercial banks are among the main financial institutions in the financial system that provide a wide range of financial services to clients and trade securities in the capital market. Their activities are organized in accordance with the legislation and regulatory framework of the country in which they operate. Banks perform various roles in the financial market: they may participate as issuers,

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60, dated January 28, 2022.

investors, or investment intermediaries². In some countries, banks also perform depository functions. Issuers have the right to place securities either independently or through banks and investment intermediaries. At the same time, banks and investment intermediaries may enter into contracts with issuers under which they assume the obligation to purchase the unsubscribed portion of issued securities or act solely as intermediaries in selling them on behalf of the issuer³.

Looking at international experience, in some countries banks operate in the form of separate investment banks. Investment banks are financial institutions specialized primarily in securities-related operations, and their main function is to raise additional capital from financial markets and to provide long-term financing to clients, including the government⁴. At the same time, in recent years the distinction between commercial and investment banking activities has been significantly diminishing, as commercial banks are increasingly expanding their involvement in investment operations.

Analysis and results

The results of the analysis show that by developing the issuance of securities, investment activities, and intermediation services, it is possible to significantly meet the financial needs of enterprises in our country. These processes can also be observed directly through examples from international practice. At the same time, in order to expand the activities of commercial banks in the capital market in our country, it is important to reconsider the relationships between issuers and clients, establish new investment directions, and raise the qualifications of banking specialists to the level of modern technologies.

International practice shows that by operating in the securities market, banks are able to expand the scope of their operations. In developed countries, commercial banks make extensive use of capital market instruments, and sufficient economic and legal frameworks have been created to support such activities.

Currently, there are 35 commercial banks operating in Uzbekistan⁵, but their participation in the securities market remains limited. This is due to several factors, including the insufficient development of the capital market, the inability of banks to expand their investment activities in the securities market, or the lack of operations aligned with the practices of foreign banks. At the same time, although the number of private banks and banks with foreign capital participation is 2.5 times higher than the number of banks with state ownership, the overall level of commercial banks' activity in the securities market is still not high. For example, as of the end of 2023, only 5.5 percent of commercial banks' total interest income was derived from income from securities⁶.

Under the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, commercial banks are allowed to conduct the following main operations in the securities market⁷:

- issuance of securities;
- purchase and sale of securities;

² Elmirzayev, S., et al. (2019). [Title not provided]. Tashkent: Iqtisod-Moliya Publishing House, 222 p.

³ Elmirzayev, S., et al. (2019). Tashkent: Iqtisod-Moliya Publishing House, 224 p.

⁴ Shokhazamiy, Sh. Sh. (2012). *Financial Market and Securities*. Textbook. Tashkent: Fan va Texnologiya Publishing House, 199 p.

⁵ Annual Report of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan – 2024.

⁶ Annual Report of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan – 2024.

⁷ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-580, dated November 5, 2019.

- maintenance and custody of securities accounts;
- management of securities and the execution of other related operations based on contracts concluded with clients.

In Uzbekistan, the primary activity of commercial banks in the securities market is the issuance of securities. In addition, banks may also operate as underwriters in the capital market. An example of this is the placement of shares of the joint-stock company “Kvars” by the National Bank for Foreign Economic Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan. When commercial banks participate in the securities market as investors, they gain the opportunity to invest in various financial instruments.

Figure 1. Dynamics of market prices of the Top 5 most liquid securities in 2023⁸.

Figure 1 illustrates the market price dynamics of the Top 5 most liquid securities in 2023. In this ranking, securities issued by commercial banks occupy leading positions. In particular, the ordinary shares of JSC “Ipak Yo‘li” increased by 212.90 percent, while the preferred shares of JSC “Ipoteka Bank” rose by 69.12 percent. At the same time, the ordinary shares of JSC “O‘zsanoatqurilishbank” declined in value by 4.49 percent. These results reflect the liquidity of commercial banks’ securities and their role in price fluctuations in the capital market.

⁸ Prepared by the author based on the stock exchange annual reports.

Below, we review the trading data of the Tashkent Republican Stock Exchange.

Figure 2. Top 10 stocks by number of transactions (units)⁹.

According to the data in Figure 2, during 2023 the highest number of transactions was recorded for the shares of JSC “O‘zsanoatqurilishbank” (SQBN), totaling 87,530 transactions. At the same time, the number of transactions involving the shares of JSC “Hamkorbank” (HMKB) reached 27,452. The lowest position in the Top-10 ranking was occupied by the ordinary shares of JSC “Uzbekistan Republican Commodity Exchange” (URTS), with a total of 10,626 transactions.

Figure 3. Top 10 stocks by transaction volume (billion UZS)¹⁰.

According to the data presented in Figure 3, in 2023 the highest trading volume was recorded for the ordinary shares of JSC “OCTOBANK” (OCBK), with a total volume of 157.35 billion UZS. The second position was occupied by the shares of JSC “PERFECT INSURANCE” (PFIS) and JSC “UzAuto Motors” (UZMT), with trading volumes of 51.60 billion UZS and 24.14 billion UZS, respectively. The lower end of the Top-10 ranking was represented by the shares of JSC “OHANGARONSEMENT” (OHSM), with a trading volume of 5.00 billion UZS.

⁹ Prepared by the author based on stock exchange data.

¹⁰ Prepared by the author based on stock exchange data.

An analysis of the indicators shown in Figures 2 and 3 demonstrates that commercial banks occupy a leading position in terms of both the number and volume of share transactions. However, these stock market trading indicators do not necessarily imply that banks are actively engaged in investment operations in securities. For example, JSC “OCTOBANK” did not conduct any share-purchase operations during the period 2012–2021¹¹. At the same time, it is evident that the active investment participation of commercial banks in the securities market has not yet reached a significant level.

Table.1

Transaction volumes of commercial banks in securities by year (billion UZS)¹².

Industries	2019 y	%	2020 y	%	2021 y	%	2022 y	%	2023 y	%
Banks	319.5	-	326,7	1.02	312.61	0.95	2 308.67	7.38	971.97	0.42

According to the data in Table 1, the transaction volume of banks in the securities market reached its highest level in 2022, while the lowest figure was recorded in 2021.

Table. 2

Bond trading indicators on the stock exchange in 2023 (Top 5)¹³.

Tiker	Bitimlar soni, dona	Qim. qogʻ. soni, dona	Bitimlar hajmi, mlrd soʻm
KBPA10	1	6 180	64 410.00
HKIL3	12	13 651	13 651.00
IFMT3	215	6 227	6 218.00
BFMT3	125	4 299	4 330.00

According to the data in Table 2, the largest trading volume was recorded for the bonds of JSC “Kapitalbank” (KBPA10), with a total value of 64.41 billion UZS, which accounts for 69.88 percent of the total bond market trading volume. At the same time, as of the end of 2023, the quotation list of the “Tashkent” Republican Stock Exchange included 8 bonds issued by 7 issuers. Of these, two were joint-stock companies, two belonged to the banking sector, and the remaining three were issued by limited liability companies.

Conclusions and recommendations

The results of the analysis indicate that the activities of commercial banks in the securities market of Uzbekistan are promising, and their participation in the capital market is of significant importance not only for the banks themselves but also for the national economy. However, at present, banks’ activities in the securities market are not sufficiently developed. Taking this into account, the following recommendations can be proposed:

- to expand business activities and create new sources of investment income by establishing dedicated units within commercial banks that specialize in securities investment;

¹¹ <https://octobank.uz/uz/shareholders/disclosures/repurchase-of-shares/>

¹² Prepared by the author based on the stock exchange annual reports.

¹³ Stock exchange analysis for the end of 2023.

- to further improve the legislation regulating the activities of commercial banks in the securities market;
- to significantly reduce the state's share in commercial banks, which would have a positive impact on the development of the secondary securities market.
- Banks should actively issue securities in order to attract low-cost financial resources and establish the necessary infrastructure to support this process.

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